

Desirability Mechanisms and Teachers' Job Retention in Private Secondary Schools in Delta State

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Abstract

This study examined desirability mechanism and teachers job retention in private secondary schools in Delta State. It was guided by two research questions and one null hypothesis. This study was a correlational survey that employed the ex-post facto design. The sample for this study was 1533 and it is made up of 588 proprietors/principals and 945 teachers in Delta State private secondary schools selected from 12 Local Government Areas. The sampling procedure used was a stratified random sampling technique. The instrument that was used for the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled 'Desirability Mechanism Questionnaire' (DMQ) and Teachers Job Retention Questionnaire' (DMTJRQ). The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha test of reliability and yielded 0.96. The data was statistically analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation to answer the research questions while, Pearson Product Moment Statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The study found out that desirability mechanism for teachers' job retention includes; training and career development, allowances, consideration for promotion, job security and pension. It was recommended that principals/proprietors should encourage training and career development for teachers. Also, principals/ proprietors should improve pay package, pay allowances, provide job security and consider teachers for promotion as these have impact on job retention. The study affirmed that desirability mechanism such as training and career development for teachers, pay allowances and consider teachers for promotion influence teachers' job retention in private secondary schools in Delta State.

Keywords: Desirability Mechanism, Job Retention, Private Schools

Introduction

The quality of teachers in all aspect forms the fundamental school-related factor in contemporary education. Researches around the globe show that teachers have a decisive contribution to students' achievements and improvement given the fact that they impart knowledge and morals that result in capacity building and ideological transformation that make students useful and productive members of the society (Chetty, Friedman & Rockoff, 2014). Furthermore, the educational goal of any nation can never be achieved without an adequately trained and motivated teaching staff. Consequently, for teachers to give optimum productivity, their satisfaction is of utmost importance.

Teachers' satisfaction among other things is hinged on the availability of basic facilities of teaching and learning, conducive physical and social environment, good pay package that help to motivate teachers to work, and act as a desirability mechanism through which teachers loyalty and retention is achievable. Teachers' willingness to stay on the job is a function of job desirability which flows from management's strategies put in place to make sure they are satisfied and motivated. Job desirability in this case does not imply the quest for jobs arising from scarcity that make employees (teachers) want to keep the available one but mechanisms employed by school administrators to retain its teaching staff. .

Teachers' retention forms an important aspect in teaching, resource planning and management practices. Entire employee planning efforts, including training, are totally meaningless if such employees cannot be properly retained. Evidence shows that teachers' retention is a critical problem in private schools in Nigeria (Akande, 2014). Every school, whether public or private, strives to recruit a pool of qualified and committed teaching staff that can deliver quality education to its students and in turn produce students of high quality. Therefore, it is crucial for schools to retain talented teaching staff. When the qualified teachers for any reason have intentions of leaving the school system or teaching field, it would portend a negative impact on students and the institution's overall performance as well. Thus, it is essential to retain highly qualified teachers in the school system on continuous basis for quality education delivery. In many secondary schools in Nigeria, the working and living conditions of many teachers are very poor, especially those in the private sector, irrespective of the fact that they are arguably the most important group of professionals in the development of the nation.

Teachers' job desirability mechanisms are principally organizational packages put in place that go beyond reward system in the form of salary. They include such things as basic pay strategies (which comprises of short-term and long term incentive, basic salary/wage, premium pay, cash recognition, annual

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bonuses, shares and profit sharing). We also have benefit rewards (health care, retirement (pensions) and work like benefits. This accounts for an increasing portion of the reward package for workers, career rewards (training and development, lateral move/advancement, stretch assignments, personal growth via career incentives and employment security. It as well covers non-financial rewards (recognition, praise, achievement, responsibility and professional growth, a pleasant working environment, being involved in decisions that affect how and when employees do their work, creative rewards, etc.). Thus, it is the total reward management strategy such as all other reward management strategies that are available to the employer (Armstrong, 2017).

Teachers' Desirability Mechanism

Desirability mechanisms also referred to as welfare package in this study has been defined in various ways by many authors. Yoder (2018) define the term desirability mechanism as a wide variety of services provided by organizations for employees, and in some cases, for members of employees' families. Shubin (2017) sees it as additional incentives given to employees' by management to augument their wages. Moreover, Ejiafor (2016) perceives employee welfare package from monetary and non-monetary perspectives when he defines it as something of value, apart from agreed regular monetary payments of salaries and wages given by an employer to an employee. A fine distinction is made by Ejiofor between benefits and service. According to him, benefits are when direct monetary reward accrues to the individual worker. For example, pension, leave pay, and salary advance, while services involve, no direct and identifiable monetary benefit. It is in line with this the Ekpiken (2013) describe welfare programme as including the provision of well ventilated offices, drinking water, end-of year parties, rest rooms, toilet, and first aid facilities by the management to the employees. Fozia and Sabir (2016) inform that welfare packages are the total compensation and remuneration for workers that contain provision for vacation, study leave, sick leave, relocation expenses, paid holiday, staff training, transportations and accommodation benefits among others.

Teachers' desirability mechanism can also be seen as strategies employed in motivating teachers for better job performance. These are in form of salary increment, gratuity, and regular promotion, ensuring job security and establishing cordial relationship among teachers. Nigeria has embarked on a major transformation with a vision to move from a peasant society to a modern and prosperous country and education is seen as a key factor for the achievement of this objective. Desirability mechanisms are critical element of human resources management system and should be designed to work together with other

elements of the system (Oyetakin, Ajalode & Alen, 2018). It is generally believed that money not only helps people to attain their basic needs, but it is also instrumental in providing higher level need performance. As a result, most employees value work according to how much they gain from it. In most developing countries, the salary scales for secondary school teachers are not lucrative despite the rapidly increasing costs of living with very small salary increments awarded based on seniority experience, with little or no link with actual job performance (Michael, 2012). Welfare is concerned with the total wellbeing of employees both at school and at home (Armstrong, 2006).

The term teacher's welfare scheme or packages 'is interpreted to mean the provision of a minimal level of well-being and social support (Bamusananire, 2007). Dale (2006) specifically define teachers welfare packages as referring to teachers' health status and happiness, as well as their safety, although he does not provide what constitutes teachers' happiness. According to Jepkemoi (2014) the provision of well-being to teachers is a source of earning and satisfaction which is likely to increase their productivity because they are motivated and happy. Dessler (2008) supports the same view when he comments that organizations provide welfare facilities to their employees to keep their motivation levels high. When teachers are motivated and satisfied their performance increases to improve their productivity. Cole (2006) theoretically concludes that people join organizations in order to meet and satisfy their needs through statutory and non- statutory welfare programmes.

Teachers' Job Retention in Secondary Schools

Human capital represents the human factor in an organisation. It is the combination of intelligence, skills and expertise that gives an organisation its distinctive characteristics and human comparative advantage. This human factor is otherwise referred to as personnel in the social organisation. Personnel simply refer to a group of person that has a job title to perform in an organisation (Armstrong, 2010). The personnel are also the employees in a firm or establishment. Therefore the importance of personnel in an organisation or establishment cannot be overemphasized because they served as basis upon which the entire system revolves. It is the personnel which ensure adequate utilization of other resources for the common interest of the educational sector in Nigeria. This implies that adequacy of personnel in an establishment contribute significantly to the successful attainment of the organizational goals and vice versa. In view of the above, secondary level of education becomes consolidating stage for the gains of the primary education and a transiting stage for the tertiary level of education.

Secondary level of education refers to the type of education receive after primary education and

before tertiary education. It aimed at providing functional education to the youth (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2013). Functional education emphasizes utilitarian purposes which deal with the preparation of the students for useful living in the society. To achieve its set objective, the Secondary level of education, needs dynamic and committed teachers who are willing to remain in the teaching profession without any turnover intentions and contribute to the successful attainment of the educational objectives.

Teachers' retention especially at the Secondary level of education refers to the steps or practices put in place to motivate the personnel by the management to stay in the schools in order to prevent its competent and valuable workforce from leaving their job. It involves taking appropriate measures to encourage teachers to remain in the teaching profession for a maximum period of time (Hong et al., 2012). This implies that maximum productivity can be achieved in any organisation by optimising the effectiveness of the employees, improving the life span of employees and treating employees as valuable assets. It further means, addressing the needs of teachers to enhance their job satisfaction thereby reducing the tendency of quitting the teaching job.

Security is one of the second fundamental needs of man as postulated by Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Langbert (2002) asserted that security needs are essential needs; for physical safety and the desire to be free from the fear of deprivation of the physiological needs. It is largely observed that once an employee on the job passes the probationary period, the need for job security quickly appears to recede its importance. As this is achieved, the individual becomes relaxed and complacent in a job situation.

Lankford (2012) opined that job security is both intrinsic and extrinsic values. It is a paramount consideration of most workers in deciding how long they intend to stay on a job. Lankford (2015) further emphasized that job security is indispensable in any work organisation. This is because it guarantees staff members' retention in the system and its absence threatens stability and spells doom for the organisation. Job insecurity can be seen as one of the socio-psychological problems which are predominant in the developing countries such as Nigeria. It is characterised by poor wages, loss of pay, issue of downsizing, lack of accommodation, lack of consideration for promotion, possibility of dismissal and application of draconian rules. Job insecurity tends to result in a sense of worthlessness and bleak future for an individual worker or teacher in such a system. The absence of job security is responsible for the high turnover rate of teacher. Research findings abound which indicate that when teachers are dissatisfied with their jobs as a result of lack of job security they respond to the situation by seeking other jobs and leaving teaching profession.

Statement of Problem

One of the challenges private schools are facing in Nigeria, particularly in Delta State is the inability to retain its staff for a very long time. This situation is in some ways connected to reward system (salary) and packages put in place to attract and retain talented staff who will contribute to the overall growth and development of the school through knowledge impartation and mentorship given to students particularly at the secondary school level where they are prepared for career choice in the future. Teachers like every other employee are motivated to work and remain in an organization (school) where there are strategies which can be called desirability mechanism, put in place to meet their needs. The availability of these attractive measures help to retain as well as get the best out of employees who feel that their welfare is of utmost concern to management. This make teachers' desirability mechanisms core to the growth and development of educational institutions most importantly at the private sector which partly operates without government involvement since it is privately funded.

The situation in most private schools in Delta State reveal that management seem to prioritize profit making at the detriment of staff welfare and this is seen in the nearly zero salary scheme that is put in place as a reward system for staff. Teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State appear to suffer from lack of career development and growth opportunities. The only challenging task which teachers have that has a negative reinforcing effect, is being saddled with the responsibility of teaching about four to five or more subjects to save money on the part of management, and in most cases without available instructional materials to ease the burden of lesson note planning. This situation has prompted the researcher to put the statement of the problem in a question form which is: What are the desirability mechanism available in private secondary schools and how do these influence teachers' job retention in Delta State?

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. What is the profile of desirability mechanisms among private secondary schools in Delta State?
2. What is the average job retention rate among teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between desirability mechanism and teachers' job retention in Delta State private secondary schools

Methodology

This study is a correlational survey adopting the ex-post-facto research design. The population of the study was 15,951 comprising of 1177 proprietors/principals and 14,774 teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State in the twenty-five (25) Local Government Areas of Delta State. The sample for this study was 1533 and it was made up of 588 proprietors/principals and 945 teachers in Delta State private secondary schools selected from 12 Local Government Areas. Proprietors/principals represented 50% while teachers represent 10% of the population using the simple random sampling technique. The instruments that were used for the study was self-developed questionnaires titled ‘Desirability Mechanism Questionnaire’ (DMQ) and Teachers Job Retention Questionnaire’ (TJRQ) designed for both Proprietors / Principals and Teachers. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha test of reliability with a reliability index of 0.97. Descriptive statistic of mean scores and standard deviation and coefficient of determination using 2.50 as benchmark which provided answers to the research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistic was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the profile of desirability mechanisms among private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Analysis on Profile of Desirability Mechanisms

SN	Profile of Desirability Mechanisms	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Training and career development	2.96	.83	+
2.	Allowances	3.18	.77	+
3.	Consideration for promotion	3.14	.81	+
4.	Job security	3.04	.75	+
5.	Pension	2.96	.78	+
6.	Appraisal at the end of each term	3.16	.79	+
Grand Mean Score		3.03	.79	+

Keys: + = Agree, - = Disagree

Data in Table 1 shows mean scores and standard deviation analysis on profile of desirability mechanisms. The result shows that respondents agreed on all the items with mean scores above 2.50 benchmark for the study. Thus, profile of desirability mechanisms is by training and career development for teachers, pay allowances, teachers are considered for promotion, job security, pay pension as at when due and appraisal at the end of each term.

Research Question 2: What is the average job retention rate among teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Analysis on Average Job Retention Rate

SN	Average Job Retention Rate	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Teachers job retention is influenced by career development opportunities	2.94	.84	+
2.	Teachers job retention is influenced by job security	2.80	.76	+
3.	Teacher job retention is influenced by pay package	2.84	.82	+
4.	Teachers’ job retention is influenced by quality learning environment	3.06	.89	+
5.	Teachers’ job retention is influenced by good management-employees relationship	3.16	.79	+
Grand Mean Score		2.97	.81	+

Keys: + = Agree, - = Disagree

Data in Table 2 shows mean scores and standard deviation analysis on job retention rate among teachers in private secondary schools in Delta State. The result shows that respondents agreed on all the items with mean scores above 2.50 benchmark for the study. Thus, teachers’ job retention is influenced by career development opportunities, teachers’ job retention is influenced by job security, teachers’ job retention is influenced by pay package, teachers’ job retention is influenced by quality learning environment and teachers’ job retention is influenced by good management-employees relationship.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between desirability mechanism and teachers job retention in Delta State private secondary schools.

Table 3: Pearson “r” on Desirability Mechanism and Teachers Job Retention

Variables	N	\bar{X}	DF	r-Cal.	r-Crit.	Level of Sign	Decision
Desirability mechanism	1533	2.96	1530	0.132	0.062	0.05	Significant
Teachers’ job retention		2.82					

Data in Table 3 revealed Pearson product moment correlation coefficient analysis on desirability mechanism and teachers job retention. The mean was 2.96 and 2.82 for desirability mechanism and teachers job retention respectively. The calculated r - value was 0.132 while the critical r-table value was 0.062 with DF of 1530 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated r - value was greater than the critical r-table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between desirability mechanism and teachers job retention in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

Desirability Mechanism and Teachers Job Retention

Findings showed that desirability mechanism for teachers’ job retention include; training and career development, allowances, consideration for promotion, job security and pension. The hypothesis tested showed that there was a significant relationship between desirability mechanism and teachers job

retention in public secondary schools in Delta State. This is in line with Shubin (2017) who sees incentives given to employees' by management to augment their wages. Moreover, Ejiafor (2016) perceives employee welfare package from monetary and non-monetary perspectives when he defines it as something of value, apart from agreed regular monetary payments of salaries and wages given by an employer to an employee. A fine distinction is made by Ejiofor between benefits and service. According to him, benefits are when direct monetary reward accrues to the individual worker. For example, pension, leave pay, and salary advance, while services involve, no direct and identifiable monetary benefit. It is in line with this that Ekpiken (2013) described welfare programme as including the provision of well-ventilated offices, drinking water, end-of year parties, rest rooms, toilet, and first aid facilities by the management to the employees. Fozia and Sabir (2016) inform that welfare packages are the total compensation and remuneration for workers that contain provision for vacation, study leave, sick leave, relocation expenses, paid holiday, staff training, transportations and accommodation benefits among others.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that desirability mechanism for teachers' job retention includes training and career development for teachers, payment of allowances, consideration for promotion, job security and payment of pension when due. Hence if these desirability mechanisms are put in place, teachers' job retention will be enhanced.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals/proprietors should encourage training and career development for teachers.
2. Principals/proprietors should pay allowances and consider teachers for promotion.
3. Principals/proprietors should career growth for teachers to promote commitment and result in job satisfaction.

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